

THE PREDOMINANCE OF GLOBAL LEXICAN IN YOUTH SPEECH

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Annotatsiya. Mazkur maqolada globalizatsiya jarayonining yoshlar nutqiga ko'rsatayotgan ta'siri, xususan global leksikaning ustunlik kasb etishi masalasi tahlil qilinadi. Tadqiqotda yoshlar nutqida ingliz tilidan kirib kelayotgan so'zlar, internatsional birliklar va raqamli kommunikatsiyaga xos qisqartmalar faol qo'llanayotgani yoritiladi. Shuningdek, global leksikaning qo'llanishi natijasida milliy til birliklarining siqilib borishi, semantik o'zgarishlar hamda madaniy konnotatsiyalarning transformatsiyasi ko'rib chiqiladi. Maqolada yoshlar nutqining zamonaviy tendensiyalari lingvokulturologik va sotsiolingvistik yondashuvlar asosida tahlil qilinib, global va milliy omillar o'rtasidagi o'zaro munosabat ochib beriladi.

Kalit so'zlar: globalizatsiya, global leksika, yoshlar nutqi, lingvokulturologiya, sotsiolingvistika, til o'zgarishi, inglizcha o'zlashmalar, raqamli kommunikatsiya, madaniy konnotatsiya, semantik transformatsiya

Annotation. This article analyzes the impact of the globalization process on youth speech, in particular, the dominance of global lexicon. The study highlights the active use of words from English, international units, and abbreviations specific to digital communication in youth speech. It also examines the compression of national language units, semantic changes, and the transformation of cultural connotations as a result of the use of global lexicon. The article analyzes modern trends in youth speech based on linguoculturological and sociolinguistic approaches, revealing the relationship between global and national factors.

Key words: globalization, global lexicon, youth speech, linguoculturology, sociolinguistics, language change, English borrowings, digital communication, cultural connotation, semantic transformation

Аннотация. В данной статье анализируется влияние процесса глобализации на речь молодежи, в частности, доминирование глобального лексикона. Исследование подчеркивает активное использование слов из английского языка, международных единиц и сокращений, специфичных для цифровой коммуникации, в речи молодежи. Также рассматривается сжатие национальных языковых единиц, семантические изменения и трансформация культурных коннотаций в результате использования глобального лексикона. В статье анализируются современные тенденции в речи молодежи на основе лингвокультурологического и социолингвистического подходов, выявляя взаимосвязь между глобальными и национальными факторами.

Ключевые слова: глобализация, глобальный лексикон, речь молодежи, лингвокультурология, социолингвистика, языковые изменения, заимствования из английского языка, цифровая коммуникация, культурная коннотация, семантическая трансформация

In the current era of globalization, the interaction between language and culture is reaching a new level. As a result of the rapid development of information technologies, the widespread use of the Internet and social networks, communication between the peoples of the world has become significantly more active. This process is especially evident in the speech of young people, leading to the widespread use of global lexicon in their language. Modern young people actively use words borrowed from English, international units, and abbreviations specific to digital communication in their daily communication.

The dominance of global lexicon in youth speech is noteworthy not only as a linguistic, but also as a cultural phenomenon. Because language is not only a means of communication, but also an expression of national thought and culture. The expansion of global lexicon, in turn, has its impact

on the national language system, in some cases causing traditional lexical units to become obsolete or their semantic changes. [1]At the same time, this process also directly affects the worldview, values, and communicative behavior of young people.

The relevance of this article is determined by the need to scientifically analyze the global lexical changes observed in youth speech and to determine their impact on language and culture.[5] The purpose of the study is to determine the degree of dominance of global lexis in youth speech in the context of globalization, to reveal its linguoculturological and sociolinguistic features.[2] Based on this goal, the article analyzes the sources, scope, and impact of global lexis on the national language.

Language changes resulting from globalization processes are clearly and rapidly observed, especially in the speech of young people. Young people, as the most active and innovative stratum of society, widely use global means of communication, which leads to the dominance of global vocabulary in their speech. Global vocabulary refers mainly to words imported from English, international terms, and units specific to digital communication. [3]Such units not only satisfy the communicative needs of young people in their speech, but also serve as a means of expressing modernity, openness, and involvement in global culture.

As a result of the dominance of the global lexicon, certain changes are taking place in the lexical-semantic system of the language. On the one hand, global units are necessary to express new concepts, on the other hand, they can lead to the suppression of national equivalents[4]. For example, the word *like* is replacing the verbs *yoktirmoq* or *ma'qullamoq* in the Uzbek language. At the same time, some global units are acquiring a new semantic load and creating a unique connotative meaning. [6] This process leads to a transformation in the semantic system of the language.

When analyzing this phenomenon from a linguo-cultural point of view, it is determined that the global lexicon also affects the cultural identity of young people. The use of global words is often perceived as a sign of modernity, freedom and proximity to international culture. As a result, elements of national and global culture are combined in youth speech, forming a new communicative model. However, this process can in some cases lead to the weakening or relegation of national cultural values to a secondary position.

From a sociolinguistic point of view, the level of use of global vocabulary varies depending on the social environment, level of education and communicative needs of young people. While global units are more common in the speech of young people living in urban environments and actively using the Internet, such units are less common in the speech of young people in relatively traditional environments. This indicates that the impact of globalization has a socially differential nature.

Thus, although the dominance of global vocabulary in youth speech is manifested as a natural process in the development of language, it has a significant impact on the national language system and culture. An in-depth analysis of this process and identification of its positive and negative aspects is one of the pressing issues of modern linguistics.

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